

THE INFLUENCE OF SELF-EFFICACY AND PARENT'S SOCIAL SUPPORTS ON ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION OF STUDENTS IN YP GKPI JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL, RAWAMANGUN, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

This present study is intended to investigate the influence of self-efficacy and parent's social supports on academic procrastination of students in YP GKPI junior high school, Rawamangun, Indonesia. Since the population comprising 58 students, a small number of population, this study employed a census method. The instrument involved an academic procrastination scale (34 items), self-efficacy scale (25 items), and parent's social support scale (33 items). The result of multiple regression analysis reveals that the value of $p < 0.05$, meaning that self-efficacy and parent's social support altogether contribute to the academic procrastination behavior significantly. On the other hand, the variable of parent's social support does not significantly contribute to academic procrastination of the students. This is based on the result of coefficient table that the value of $p > 0.05$.

Keywords: self-efficacy, parent's social support, academic procrastination behavior

1. Introduction

Ferrari (1995) defines procrastination as an action of delaying or postponing works and decision-making. The term academic procrastination is a tendency to postpone or deny responsibilities, decisions, or jobs that should be accomplished (Haycook, McCarthy & Skay, 1998). Some examples of such negative behaviors are working on assignments and preparing for examinations a night before the due date or the test date despite the fact that the students must prepare themselves earlier.

Numerous studies on academic procrastination behaviors have reported some factors affecting such negative habits; one of the factors is self-efficacy, i.e., the internal factor from the person. Bandura (1997) explains the term self-efficacy as a person's

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confidence in their ability to organize and to carry out a set of activities in achieving individual goals. Students with high self-efficacy work on their assignments immediately. These students are also determined to meet their target. On the other hand, those who have low self-efficacy tend to postpone their academic works (Ellis & Knaus, 2002). Self-confidence, i.e., believing self-ability is central to the success of students in learning.

Another factor affecting academic procrastination behavior is from the external of the student, such as parent's social support. This type of support refers to the way the parent show their affection to the students. Some of the examples are acceptance, provision of help, as well as showing care and giving rewards to children. Support from the parent contributes to the development of motivation and perseverance of children in an academic setting and thus enhancing the children's achievement. Ferrary and Olivette (1994) opine that poor support from parents can lead to procrastination behavior indirectly.

2. Research Methodology

A questionnaire was distributed to the population of this quantitative study. The population involved 58 students in grade VII, VIII, and IX in YP GKPI Junior High School, Rawamangun. The data were collected using a Likert scale model. Furthermore, the instrument consisted of three types, i.e., academic procrastination scale, self-efficacy scale, and parent's social support scale.

The academic procrastination scale is designed based on the indicator by Ferrari and Olivette (1994). The indicator consists of several aspects, such as postponing to work and accomplish assignments, delaying to work assignments, the time gap between plan and actual performance, and doing more enjoyable activities. The scale of self-efficacy used an indicator of measurement by Bandura (1997) comprising of components, namely level of difficulty, generality, and strength. Lastly, the social support variable is measured using a social provisions scale by Robert Weiss (1974). The elements of this scale involve attachment, social integration, the reassurance of worth, reliable alliance, guidance, and opportunity for nurturance.

The data of this present study were scrutinized using a multiple regression analysis method. This method is intended to examine the extent to which the two independent variables, i.e., self-efficacy and parent's social support affect the dependent variable, i.e., academic procrastination. Furthermore, a program called SPSS version 16 for Windows was also used in the data analysis process.

3. Material and Methods

Procrastination is among the issues in education that commonly occurred in the learning process. This issue blames internal factor from the student, such as self-efficacy, and external factor, such as parent's social support. The problem of procrastination is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

4. Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: Self-efficacy and parent's social supports altogether influence academic procrastination of students in YP GKPI junior high school, Rawamangun.

Hypothesis 2: Self-efficacy influences academic procrastination of students in YP GKPI junior high school, Rawamangun.

Hypothesis 3: Parent's social support influences academic procrastination of students in YP GKPI junior high school, Rawamangun.

5. Results and Discussion

The results of data analysis using the SPSS program are as follows:

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.919 ^a	.844	.839	8.96898		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Parent's Social Support, Self-efficacy						
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23999.810	2	11999.905	149.173	.000 ^a
	Residual	4424.345	55	80.443		
	Total	28424.155	57			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Parent's Social Support, Self-efficacy						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	186.425	4.281		43.552	.000
	Self-efficacy	-1.014	.114	-.942	-8.899	.000
	Parent's Social Support	.018	.070	.027	.254	.800
a. Dependent Variable: Procrastination						

The result of multiple regression analysis reveals that the value of R = 0.919 and R-square = 0.844, where F = 149.173 with the significance level at 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This

result suggests that the self-efficacy and parent's social support significantly contribute to the academic procrastination behavior with a percentage of 84.4%. The remaining 15.6% refers to other variables excluded from this present study.

This condition also applies to the variable of self-efficacy. The result of coefficient table analysis reveals that the value of beta (β) = -0.942 with the significance level at 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). In other words, the variable of self-efficacy significantly contributes to academic procrastination behavior.

On the other hand, the result of coefficient table analysis for the variable of parent's social support reveals that the value of beta (β) = 0.027 with the significance level at 0.800 ($p > 0.05$). This finding indicates that the variable of parent's social support does not contribute to the academic procrastination behavior significantly.

6. Discussion

This research finds that the self-efficacy and parent's social support significantly contribute to the academic procrastination behavior, where $F = 149.173$ with the significance level at 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) with a percentage of 84.4%. Such a finding resonates to the theory by Ellis & Knaus (2002) that students with high self-efficacy work on their assignments immediately and are determined to meet their target. On the other hand, those who have low self-efficacy tend to postpone their academic works. Self-confidence, i.e., believing self-ability is central to the success of students in learning. Furthermore, the finding of this present study is in line with the result seen in Lee, Bong and Kim (2004) that self-efficacy has a significant influence on academic procrastination. On the other hand, this study finds out that the variable of parent's social support gets the value of beta (β) = 0.027 with the significance level at 0.800 ($p > 0.05$). This finding reveals that the variable of parent's social support does not contribute to the academic procrastination behavior significantly. Ferrari (1995) asserts that external factors of an individual, e.g., parenting and environmental situation, can affect procrastination behaviors in an academic setting.

The result seen in this present study is supported by Bandura's theory (1986) that a person requires high self-confidence to carry out their works.

7. Recommendations

Drawing on the result of this study and data analysis, the recommendations are as follows:

A. Theoretical Recommendations

In addition to the opinion by Ferrari (1995) regarding the influence of internal factors on students' procrastination, the psychological condition of learners has a significant contribution to the behavior of procrastination in an academic setting. Environment condition and parenting, the external factors, also affect such negative behavior. Therefore, future research is urged to examine the effect of physical condition, parenting, and environmental condition. In-depth investigations with wider scope

regarding the academic procrastination are also necessary; the studies should be conducted in all level of education, not only in junior high level.

B. Practical Recommendations

- This present study shows that a high level of students' self-efficacy reduces the number of procrastination issues among students. Such a finding suggests that students should be determined and should believe themselves to attain a satisfactory goal. This attitude can be actualized by studying diligently.
- Schools, especially teachers, are expected to provide positive supports actively to their students in learning. This is intended to motivate the students to earn the achievement in school. Furthermore, the schools should monitor the psychology of the students. Teachers are also required to be more creative in modeling positive behaviors to improve students' self-efficacy by which it overcomes the students' procrastination.

8. Conclusion

- Self-efficacy and parent's social supports altogether influence academic procrastination of the students in YP GKPI junior high school, Rawamangun.
- This study also finds that self-efficacy affects academic procrastination of the students in the research site. In other words, the higher the self-efficacy of the students, the lower the issue of academic procrastination.

On the other hand, parent's social supports do not influence academic procrastination of the students in the research site significantly. This finding suggests that there are other contributing factors of procrastination behavior.

About the Author(s)

All the activities in this article have been done by Fretty Eliana.

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